

Presentation

These articles were originally published in the Pedagogy Series, housed in the ISA's Social Justice and Democratization Space in January and June 2022. We are republishing it in order to standardize all the articles in the Sociological Teaching journal, a new space of publication from the Thematic Group 09.

Dear colleagues,

We hope you enjoy this issue of the Pedagogy Series, housed on the ISA's Social Justice and Democratization Space. Our goal in putting together this open-access publication is to create a forum for sociology educators around the world to share their teaching practices, reflections and theoretical insights rooted in the contexts where they live and work. This issue takes an applied approach, inviting educators to share how they conceptualize and approach their teaching practice, often in collaborative ways.

In our first piece, Alma Pisciotta and Luciana Taddei write from the University of Calabria, Italy about co-teaching sociological research methods through theatrical techniques. Each author reflects on their role as instructor in a component of this innovative course. They outline their "Theatrical sociology approach," designed to provide students with tools to investigate everyday social phenomena.

Our second article features a pedagogical collaboration between Melanie Bush (Adelphi University) and Nokuthula Hlabangane (University of South Africa) through a course on "The Reshaping of Social Relations in the Modern World". Both course instructors reflect on the theoretical framing for this collaboration and its impact on students, tied to engagement, heightened global awareness and cross-border kinship.

The third paper is from Australia written collaboratively by colleagues from the University of Newcastle, Swinburne University of Technology, and Curtin University. Irwin et al. critically discuss the curriculum design for the Open Foundation program offered by the University of Newcastle. The open-access program seeks to increase participation of underrepresented groups in higher education by providing students who do not meet formal admission criteria with an alternate route to university. Drawing on data generated through the Collaborative Inquiry Project, Irwin et al. argue that educators in the program had to manage the tension between providing access to higher education and a neo-liberal social context that frames educational success as an individual accomplishment and draws on market principles to justify reductions in funding for higher education. However, educators in the program remained committed to the social justice project of increasing access to higher education. Moreover, through their teaching practices educators sought to help program participants to not only become university students, but also ‘curious citizens.

We thank you for your readership.

Sincerely,

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